

ASSOCIATION BETWEEN KNOWLEDGE OF FOOD LABELS AND BODY MASS INDEX AMONG MEDICAL VS. NON-MEDICAL STUDENTS

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Abstract

Background: The consumption of processed food has increased drastically over last few decades causing an increase in diet related non-communicable diseases and increased BMI specially among students. The processed food products have food labels which provide an insight to nutritional quality of food being consumed. These food labels may play a role to lower the intake of unhealthy foods, helping people to make intentional choices towards a healthy food intake. The type of education, either medical or non-medical, can significantly impact the ability to interpret the information on food labels and may affect the food choices.

Objecti ve: To determine the difference between knowledge of food labels among medical and non-medical students and to determine the association between knowledge of food labels and BMI among both groups.

Materials and methods: A total of 241 participants were included in this study among them 121 were medical students and 120 were non-medical students. A validated questionnaire in form of Likert scale was used to assess the knowledge, attitudes and use of food labels. Fisher exact test was used to assess the difference in knowledge of food labels between both groups and spearman's correlation was used to assess the association between knowledge of food labels and BMI.

Results: The comparison of knowledge of food labels between medical and non-medical students showed that medical students had higher knowledge of food labels (55.4%) than non-medical students (43.4%) with a p value of 0.041. Overall, statistically significant weak negative correlation (spearman's correlation value of -0.151) was found between knowledge of food labels and BMI with p value of 0.019.

Conclusion: The study revealed that medical students had more knowledge of food labels than non-medical students. It further revealed that overall, there is weak correlation between knowledge of food labels and BMI.

INTRODUCTION

Over the past 30 to 40 years, many countries and regions have undergone dramatic nutritional transition characterized by high consumption of

ultra-processed foods (Popkin & Ng, 2022). Ultra-processed foods already account for more than half of the total food energy consumed in high-income

countries and one-fifth to one-third of the total food energy consumed in middle income countries (Monteiro, Cannon, Levy, et al., 2019). Food habits that were more traditional and focused on consumption of unprocessed or minimally processed foods, home-cooked dishes (even lunches) from scratch are being replaced by these relatively low-cost ultra-processed products in middle- to low-income countries (Aguirre et al., 2019).

Studies from several countries have shown that ultra-processed foods are typically energy-dense products, high in sugar, unhealthy fats, and salt, and low in dietary fiber, protein, vitamins, and minerals. The prevalence of non-communicable diseases is increasing worldwide (Annamalai & Gopichandran, 2022). Elevated intake of ultra-processed foods (UPF) has been linked to a rise in non-communicable diseases, obesity, and overweight (Pagliai et al., 2021).

With the rapid development of the national economy and changes in lifestyle, chronic non-communicable diseases (NCDs) have become the leading cause of death in China, accounting for 82% of all deaths, and this proportion will continue to increase. However, diet is an important factor that affects premature death, disability, and the development of chronic diseases (Wei et al., 2022). Results from a prospective cohort study of British adults showed that a diet high in ultra-processed foods was associated with a significant increase in the risk of obesity and abdominal obesity of 79% and 30%, respectively. Furthermore, increasing intake of ultra-processed foods was associated with an increased risk of gain in BMI, WC, and body fat by 5% or more during follow-up (Rauber et al., 2021).

Consistent evidence from studies of various designs in many countries shows that the substitution of non-ultra-processed foods with ultra-processed foods increases the risk of obesity and a range of other diet-related non-communicable diseases, as well as premature death (Monteiro, Cannon, Lawrence, et al., 2019). The World Health Organization estimates that over 1.9 billion adults who are 18 years of age or older are overweight, and over 650 million of those persons are obese (Haththotuwa et al., 2020).

Food labels are very important since they help millions of consumers choose foods that are healthier (Temple, 2020). Food labels have been

identified as potentially valuable tools to help prevent obesity and non-communicable diseases by improving dietary habits among population (Egnell et al., 2020).

Any tag, mark, picture, or other descriptive text written or printed affixed to a pre-packaged food container is referred to as a “Food Label”. Nutritional labeling provides information on a product’s nutritional makeup, including protein, fat, carbohydrates, food additives, and preservatives, through its packaging. Therefore, nutrition labels are essential resources for educating customers about the food’s nutritional qualities and any associated health claims (Adesina et al., 2022). Food labeling successfully decreases the overall consumption of energy and total fat among consumers, while also promoting a higher intake of vegetables. Additionally, food labeling impacts how the industry adjusts the levels of sodium and artificial trans-fat in their products (Shangguan et al., 2019).

Education level generally affects the KAP of nutrition and food labels because comprehension of the nutritional information requires a certain level of knowledge (SHI YEE et al., 2022). It appears that education has a greater impact on people’s understanding, eating habits, and ability to choose healthier foods (Farahbod et al., 2021).

The understanding of food labels is significantly influenced by the student’s discipline. Regarding understanding and using nutrition labels, medical students have more knowledge than non-medical students (Wei et al., 2022). Prior research on college-bound students, both medical and non-medical, has found that there is a high level of food label knowledge and use, with medical students having a higher level of understanding than non-medical students (Annamalai & Gopichandran, 2022). Compared to medical students, non-medical students consume more meals rich in saturated fats which increases the need to raise awareness and promote healthy diet and lifestyle among non-medical students (Saintila et al., 2024). As future role models in society, health science students can significantly contribute to raising the general public’s understanding of food labels (Riaz et al., 2022).

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Consumption of processed foods has increased drastically and is directly linked to obesity and chronic disease. Food labels are vital, that reveal key information about processed foods we eat. But there is a huge educational gradient in how well those labels are understood. Improved understanding of food labels has the potential to modify diet behavior in both medical students and non-medical students. As the access to refined food is more convenient, this study aims to develop a greater level of nutritional literacy, so individuals make better food choices rather than lining loaded with processed goods putting us at risk for adverse health effects.

AIMS & OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The following are the objectives of the study:

- To evaluate the knowledge of food labels of medical and non-medical students.
- To evaluate association between knowledge of food labels and Body Mass Index.
- To compare the knowledge of food labels and its relation to Body Mass Index of medical and non-medical students.

METHODOLOGY

This cross-sectional study was conducted in Fatima memorial hospital College of Medicine and Dentistry, Lahore, over a period of four months following ethical approval from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of Fatima Memorial College of Medicine and Dentistry. The study included medical and non-medical students of age 18-25. Participants with any chronic diseases were excluded from the study to maintain a homogenous sample that accurately reflects the general student population. A random sampling technique was employed to recruit eligible participants, ensuring an unbiased selection process. All participants provided written informed consent before participating in the study. A sample size of 241 participants was calculated using a 5% level of significance, with an anticipated prevalence of the desired outcome of 21%(Wei et al., 2022). A validated questionnaire in the form of Likert scale (12), with six different sections was used to assess the understanding and use of food labels among medical and non-medical students. The questionnaire had 6 sections: Section A: Demographic data: It included

serial number, age, gender, education whether participants were medical or non-medical students and the degree they were enrolled to. Section B: Anthropometric data: The anthropometric measurements included height in feet, weight in kg and body mass index. Section C: Consumers' use of information sources on food labeling: This section included 7 questions to determine consumers' use of information sources on food labels. Section D: Consumers' knowledge of food labels: This section included 6 questions to assess consumers' knowledge of food labels. Section E: Consumers' attitudes towards food labels: This section used 2 questions to evaluate consumers' attitude towards food labels. Section F: Consumers' practice towards food labels: This last section of questionnaire included 7 questions to determine consumers' practice towards food labels use. Data was entered and analyzed using IBM-SPSS V23. Descriptive statistics were used for categorical variables (gender, education level, BMI), frequency and percentages were employed. For continuous variables such as age, weight, and height, mean and standard deviation were measured. For comparison of KAP of food labels, Fisher's Exact Test was used. A p-value less than 5% was taken as statistically significant. For evaluating the association between KAP and BMI spearman's test was used. To compare among medical and non-medical students, data was splatted, and spearman's test was applied.

RESULTS & FINDINGS

241 students were included in the study. Among these students, 50.2% were medical students and 49.8% were non-medical students. Among medical students, 15.7% were males and 84.3% were females. As far as non-medical students are concerned 25% were males and 75% were females. The BMI ranges for medical students were as underweight 14%, healthy weight 71.9%, overweight 11.6% and obese 2.5%, while those of non-medical students were as underweight 22.5%, healthy weight 61.7%, overweight 13.3%, and obese 2.5%. The age of participants including both medical and non-medical ranges from 18 years to 25 years, with mean age of medical students 21.30 and those of non-medical students 20.10. The mean weight for medical students was 57.38 kgs while for non-medical students was 57.81 kgs. The mean height for medical

students was 1.64 m while for non-medical students was 1.65m. The comparison of knowledge of food labels between medical and non-medical students showed that medical students had higher knowledge of food labels (55.4%) than non-medical students (43.4%) with a p value of 0.041. Overall, statistically significant weak negative correlation (spearman's correlation value of -0.151) was found between knowledge of food labels and BMI with p value of 0.019. Although medical students had higher knowledge of food labels, the spearman's rho

correlation test revealed that there was no significant correlation between knowledge of food labels and BMI categories for medical students ($p = 0.701$). This suggests that while medical students possess more knowledge, it does not significantly influence their BMI. In contrast, for non-medical students, there was a significant and moderately negative correlation between knowledge of food labels and BMI categories ($p = 0.003$), indicating that their food label knowledge appears to have a more direct impact on their BMI, but the relation is moderately negative with spearman's correlation value of -0.270.

Figure Error! No text of specified style in document..1 BMI of medical and non-medical students

BMI of medical students showed that 14% students were under weight, 71.9% fall under category of healthy weight, 11.6% were overweight while only 2.5% were obese, while those of non-medical showed that 22.5% fall under category of underweight, 61.7% had healthy weight, 13.3% were overweight and only 2.5% were obese.

The Fisher's Exact test revealed that there is significance difference between knowledge of food labels between medical and non-medical students with a p value of 0.041 which is <0.05 . This finding is consistent with previous studies.

Table Error! No text of specified style in document..1 Comparison of source of knowledge of food labels

		University lectures	Social media	Shopkeepers	Nutrition camps	Total	P value
Education type	Medical students	35	70	8	8	121	0.001
	Non-medical students	11	95	9	5	120	

According to table 4.1, chi-square results revealed that there is statistically significant difference between medical and non-medical students in terms of sources from where they get knowledge about food labels with a p value <0.05 . The results revealed that 28.9% medical students get their knowledge regarding food labels from university lectures compared to only 9.2% non-medical students. While small percentage of students get knowledge from shopkeepers being 6.6% from medical students and 7.5% from non-medical students and same goes for nutrition camps with only 6.6% from medical students and 4.2% from non-medical students. However, social media remains the highest source of knowledge for both groups with 57.9% medical students and 79.2% non-medical students getting knowledge from this source. As far as the difference

between attitudes of medical and non-medical students towards food labels is concerned, the results of Fisher's Exact Test gave a p value <0.05 , thus suggesting a significant difference between attitudes of medical and non-medical students towards food labels. While use and practice of food labels was same in both groups despite the difference in knowledge.

Association between knowledge of food labels and BMI gives us a p value <0.05 thus suggesting a significance association between knowledge of food labels and BMI. But at the same time, it gives us spearman's rho value of -0.515 which indicates a weak negative relation such that increase in knowledge of food labels leads to a slight decrease in BMI which means that there must be other factors that influence BMI.

Table Error! No text of specified style in document..2 Association between knowledge of food labels and BMI among medical and non-medical students

Groups	Spearman's rho	P value
Medical students	-0.035	0.701
Non-medical students	-0.270	0.003

According to spearman's rho, there is very weak correlation but no significant association between knowledge of food labels and BMI of medical students although medical student possesses greater knowledge about food labels than non-medical students. On the other hand, there is significance association between knowledge of food labels and BMI with a p value <0.05 among non-medical students with a moderate negative relation. This suggests that although non-medical students have less knowledge but that is significantly associated with BMI such that as knowledge increases BMI tends to decrease but that relation is moderate and thus other factors also play a role.

DISCUSSIONS

The study aimed to compare the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) regarding food labels between medical and non-medical students. This study showed that medical students had more awareness about food labels (55.4%) compared to non-medical students (43.4%). Medical students tend to have more understanding about food labels as

their curriculum includes topics like nutrition and health, making comprehension of food label a key part of their education. Their training also emphasizes the importance of diet in disease prevention, as they are exposed to reliable sources of information, such as scientific literature. These results were consistent from previous study conducted in China which stated that medical students had greater understanding of food labels (39.9%) than other majors (15.6%) (Wei et al., 2022). There is another supporting study conducted in King Khalid University, Abha Saudia Arabia which concluded that medical students had greater knowledge than those studying dentistry or nursing (Riaz et al., 2022).

This result justifies that education impacts the understanding of food labels as people who are more educated have more awareness and can interpret the food labels more effectively. People with more education are typically better at understanding and analyzing food labels because they possess the knowledge and skills needed to perceive nutritional facts, serving sizes, ingredient lists, and product

claims. This is in accordance with a study conducted in Benghazi, Libya at supermarkets and shopping centers. The study revealed that level of education has direct influence with understanding of food labels (Buzgeia et al., 2023).

This study also revealed that medical students had constructive approach toward food labels than non-medical students but the use and practice towards food labels were same in both groups. They don't use this knowledge in making food choices and continue to buy food products that are ultra-processed and high in sugars and saturated fats. This suggests that having awareness is not enough, but practical implication is necessary to make better food choices. The practical behavior is determined by several factors such as cultural preferences, taste, habits, and convenience. This finding is consistent with previous study conducted in Chennai, which concluded that although medical students had a good grasp and positive attitude towards food labels, their actual usage patterns were still lacking (Annamalai & Gopichandran, 2022).

This study also concluded that practice of using food labels is lacking in both groups suggesting that medical students despite having more knowledge about food labels don't use it in their daily food buying decisions. Having knowledge about food and health risks, in terms of factual literacy, may lead an individual to consider healthy eating behaviors but did not necessarily result in them practicing those behaviors (Taleb & Itani, 2021). This is supported by the study conducted in some higher education institutes in Klang Valley which stated that although participants had positive attitudes and good knowledge about nutrition, they still made poor food choices (SHI YEE et al., 2022).

This study also concluded that there was weak negative correlation between knowledge of food labels and BMI and that was statistically significant. Further analysis revealed that although medical students had more knowledge than non-medical students, there was no significant association between their knowledge of food labels and BMI. Medical students may have more understanding about food labels, but this may not necessarily translate into behavior changes that impact their BMI. Factors such as lifestyle choices, physical activity levels, and emotional or environmental

influences on eating habits might play a larger role in determining BMI than knowledge alone. This is in accordance with study conducted in Tripoli, Lebanon among adolescents that revealed that there is no association between nutrition literacy and Body Mass Index categories (Taleb & Itani, 2021).

On the other hand, non-medical students had a weak negative correlation between knowledge of food labels and Body Mass Index which suggests that as their knowledge of food labels decreases, their BMI categories increases although it is a weak correlation. The negative correlation suggests that knowledge may have effect on the Body Mass Index of individuals, but it is affected by several other factors including physical activity, sleep cycle, genetics, and dietary patterns. It is supported by a study conducted in Afyonkarahisar, Turkey which found that individuals with their BMI in normal ranges tend to read food labels more. It also revealed that as the individuals BMI values increased, their knowledge of nutrition literacy in terms of portion control decreased (Son,2023).

CONCLUSION

This research concluded that type of education influenced awareness of food labels such that medical students had more awareness about food labels than non-medical students. However, this did not translate into their actual usage and practice. There was no significant difference between medical and non-medical students in terms of the use and application of food labels. The study further revealed a weak negative correlation between individuals' knowledge of food labels and their Body Mass Index (BMI). Comparing this association among both groups revealed that although medical students have more knowledge about food labels, their association with BMI was not significant. This suggests that having more knowledge doesn't mean that it effects the food choices or BMI. On the other hand, non-medical students showed a significant link between their understanding of food labels and BMI, although the correlation was weak and negative. This means that as their knowledge of food labels increases, their BMI tends to decrease slightly. However, the weak correlation indicates that other factors, such as physical activity, dietary patterns, sleep patterns, genetics and other factors likely play a

role in the reduction of BMI. Though type of education provides awareness regarding food labels, but it didn't influence daily food choices. Thus, a more practical approach is needed to raise awareness regarding food labels to promote healthier eating habits and better food choices.

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